

Table 2. Accessions with resistance to diseases and insect pests. Nanning, Guangxi, China.

Resistance	Accession
Blast	<i>O. rufipogon</i> : YD.2-0417, 0418, 0435, 0452, 0453, 0528, 0538, 0555, 0578, 0583, 0587, 0590, 0591, 0593, 0618, 0797, 0854, 0971, 1010, 1263, 1314, 1360, 1372 <i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1618, 1624, 1626, 1627, 1628, 1629, 1635, 1645, 1647, 1674, 1680, 1698, 1724, 1737, 1764
Bacterial blight	<i>O. rufipogon</i> : YD.2-0078, 0233, 0314, 0317, 0321, 0339, 0349, 0369, 0480, 0684, 0764, 0795, 0842, 1162, 1470, 1504 <i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1630, 1656, 1667, 1668, 1669, 1670, 1685, 1702, 1703, 1719, 1721
Brown planthopper	<i>O. rufipogon</i> : N-0471, 0513, STS-543, 2167, 2172, 2173, 2182, 2184, 2190, 2205 <i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1665, 1694, 1738, 1594, 1597, 1608, 1609, 1611, 1612, 1613, 1616, 1617, 1618, 1623, 1624, 1630, 1632, 1633, 1646, 1649, 1650, 1651, 1652, 1654, 1655, 1656, 1658, 1659, 1660, 1661
Whitebacked planthopper	<i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1592, 1593, 1594, 1595, 1596, 1608, 1609, 1641, 1642, 1643, 1661, 1671, 1673, 1674, 1675, 1684, 1685, 1686, 1692, 1694, 1695, 1696, 1697, 1698, 1701, 1702, 1703, 1704, 1712, 1713
Gall midge	<i>O. rufipogon</i> : YD.2-0352, 0686, 0869, 0899, 1296, 1373, 1422, 1536 <i>O. officinalis</i> : YD.2-1751

Pest resistance—diseases

Resistance to rice blast in a line derived from *Oryza minuta*

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Oryza minuta, a wild species of rice, is highly resistant to rice blast (BI). A line derived from a wide cross between *O. minuta* and an elite *O. sativa* breeding line, IR31917-45-3-2, hereafter referred to as *OsS*, was found to possess BI resistance. Genetic studies of this line have shown that a single gene confers resistance to isolate *PO6-6* of *Pyricularia oryzae*.

During initial screening, plants were artificially inoculated with isolate *PO6-6*, and disease reactions were scored on a 0-5 scale (Table 1). Although resistance was dominant over susceptibility, under

highly favorable conditions for BI development the homozygotes (RR) were significantly more resistant than the heterozygotes (Rr) using the *t*-test ($P < 0.001$). The mean disease rating for RR plants was 1.8 ± 0.6 (mean $\pm$ SD, $n = 21$), while that of the Rr group was 2.8 ± 1.1 ($n = 34$). To characterize this resistance further, we evaluated a homozygous line, hereafter referred to as *NIL127*, in greenhouse and field studies under upland conditions. *NIL127* was shown to be nearly isogenic to *OsS* based on analysis using molecular markers (less than 1% introgression of markers from the wild species).

To assess the resistance in *NIL127* with respect to pathogen lineages, we inoculated it with 49 isolates of *P. oryzae* representing lineages 1, 4, 7, 9, 10, 11, and 14. (A lineage is a group of isolates inferred to be related by descent, based on DNA fingerprinting and phylogenetic analysis.) In this test, each treatment consisted of a pot of 12 seedlings per line. Seedlings were inoculated by spraying with a spore suspension (10^5 spores/ml) at 21 d after sowing (dry

seeded). After inoculation, plants were incubated for 24 h at 24 °C and 100% relative humidity, then transferred to a mist room at 24 °C under natural light for 5 d. Disease reactions were scored (Table 1). Each treatment was replicated twice.

Of the 49 isolates tested, 32 (representing lineages 4, 7, and 14) were compatible on recurrent parent *OsS* (Table 1). *OsS* was not susceptible to any test isolates of lineages 1, 9, 10, or 11. *NIL127* was resistant to all test isolates of

Table 1. Characterization of *NIL127* BI resistance with respect to *P. oryzae* lineages 4, 7, and 14.

Lineage ^a	Isolate	Disease reaction ^b	
		<i>OsS</i>	<i>NIL127</i>
4	Ca1	4	0
4	Ca9	4	0
4	Ca13	3	0
4	Ca19	4	0
4	Ca27	4	0
4	Ca30	4	0
4	Ca33	4	0
4	Ca40	4	0
4	Ca42	4	0
4	Ca44	4	0
4	Ca48	4	0
4	Ca51	4	0
4	Ca52	4	4
4	Ca70	4	2
4	Ca72	4	0
4	Ca73	4	0
4	Ca74	4	0
4	Ca77	4	0
4	Ca78	4	0
4	Ca79	4	0
4	Ca80	4	4
4	Ca81	4	4
4	Ca83	4	2
4	Ca84	4	0
4	Ca87	4	0
4	Ca89	4	0
4	Ca90	4	0
4	Ca91	4	0
4	Ca93	4	0
7	BN105	4	0
7	BN117	4	0
14	BN113	4	0

^aLineage as determined by DNA fingerprinting using the probe MGR586. ^bDefinition of disease reactions: 0 = immune, no evidence of infection; 1 = resistant, with brown specks, no sporulation; 2 = moderately resistant, 1- to 2-mm long, irregularly shaped lesions with brown margins; 3 = intermediate, 5 or less, 3- to 7-mm long typical, spindle-shaped sporulating lesions per inoculated leaf; 4 = susceptible, 5 or more typical lesions per inoculated leaf, lesions often coalesce; 5 = highly susceptible, many coalesced lesions infecting 50% or more of inoculated leaf, leaf dies because of lesions.

Table 2. Evaluation of *NIL127* BI resistance in upland screening sites.

Site	Line ^a	Predominant lesion type ^b	Final percentage diseased leaf area ^c			RADPC ^d Mean	
			1991	1992	1993	1992	1993
Bangladesh	<i>NIL104</i>	4	55	75	60	21.3	29.2
	<i>NIL127</i>	1	1.5	1.1	1.5	0.3	1.0
Colombia ^e	<i>OsS</i>	4	-	-	-	-	-
	<i>NIL127</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-
Indonesia	<i>OsS</i>	4	-	81.25	100	22.80	42.9
	<i>NIL127</i>	0	-	0.05	0.01	0.11	2.5
Philippines	<i>OsS</i>	4	-	Nd ^f	71.67	Nd	18.17
	<i>NIL127</i>	0	-	Nd	0.57	Nd	0.28

^aIn most cases, *NIL127* (RR) was compared with the recurrent parent, *OsS* (rr). Sometimes, however, a susceptible sibling of *NIL127*, identified above as *NIL104* (rr), was used. *NIL104* and *OsS* are identical for the purposes of this study. ^bSee Table 1 for definition of lesion types. ^cMean of four replications. ^dRADPC = relative area under the disease progress curve; mean of four replications. ^eOnly predominant lesion type data were collected when *NIL127* and *OsS* were screened in Colombia. Tests were conducted for three consecutive seasons in two consecutive years (1992A and B and 1993A). ^fNd = no disease observed at the site in the 1992 wet season due to delay of rain. Susceptible and resistant lines alike failed to develop BI symptoms.

lineages 7 and 14 and susceptible to only three isolates of lineage 4 (Table 1).

To determine the performance of *NIL127* under diverse field conditions, we evaluated this line for BI resistance in upland sites at Joydebpur, Bangladesh; Santa Rosa, Colombia; Sitiung, West Sumatra, Indonesia; and Cavinti, Laguna, Philippines (Table 2). At least two 30-50 cm rows of each line were dry seeded parallel to the prevailing winds between one or two rows of a resistant cultivar. At the leeward end of the plot, two rows of a mixture of susceptible spreader varieties were planted perpendicular to the prevailing winds. Leaf BI severity was evaluated twice a week for 3-4 wk by estimating diseased leaf area (%) on a plot basis. In addition, at least five plants were selected at random at the peak of disease development and were evaluated for lesion type using the 0-5 scale (Table 1). The experiments were replicated three or four times. Means were calculated from the replications.

We previously observed that *NIL127* remained BI-free when planted in the IRRI blast nursery and in lowland field plots on the IRRI farm (data not shown). *NIL127* was also resistant to field populations of BI in all upland screening sites where it was tested. At the Santa Rosa, Colombia site, for example, six lineages are known to be present, yet the line has remained resistant for three seasons. Hypersensitive lesions were observed (type 0 or 1), although it was

not possible to obtain any viable BI isolates from them. On the other hand, lesions on the recurrent parent, *OsS*, were usually type 4 (susceptible) (Table 2).

Comparative transmission of two strains of rice tungro spherical virus in the Philippines

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A virulent strain of rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV), designated as strain Vt6, was found to be infecting rice plants in Midsayap, North Cotabato, Philippines. The strain could highly infect rice cultivar TKM6, which is highly resistant to the IRRI strain of RTSV, designated as strain A. We conducted comparative transmission tests to identify varieties with resistance to both strains.

We tested rice accessions from the International Rice Germplasm Center for their reaction to strain Vt6. Selected accessions had been previously identified as resistant to strain A but were susceptible to green leafhopper (GLH) according to the IRRI Entomology Unit's data base on GLH resistance. Virus-free adult GLH were given 4 d of access to rice cultivar Taichung Native 1 (TN1) infected with both rice tungro bacilliform

We conclude from these studies that *NIL127* performs well under BI stress at a variety of sites. Although the resistance in *NIL127*, presumably contributed by a resistance gene from *O. minuta* in the IR31917-45-3-2 background, may not be effective against artificial inoculation with some lineage 4 isolates, *NIL127* functions effectively in the field. The apparent susceptibility of *NIL127* to some isolates in greenhouse tests suggests that this wild species-derived resistance gene is not likely to condition durable resistance alone, although it may be a useful component in a gene pyramiding program.

For further evaluation or for use in breeding programs, *NIL127* seeds can be requested from the International Network for Genetic Evaluation in Rice under the line number WHD-IS-75-1-127. This line will be included in the International Rice Blast Nursery core collection in 1994. ■

virus and strain Vt6. Three GLH were confined for 24 h with a 6-d-old seedling in a test tube for inoculation access.

Forty seedlings (2 replications, 20 seedlings/replication) were inoculated for each variety. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted into pots and grown in screened cages until symptoms developed. An identical set of test varieties simultaneously inoculated with strain A in the same manner served as control. Rice tungro viruses were indexed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay 1 mo after inoculation.

Results showed that all of the varieties tested were resistant to strain A except for Utri Rajapan, which showed an intermediate reaction. Their reaction to strain Vt6, however, varied from highly resistant (0-10% infection ratio) to very susceptible. Twenty-nine varieties had an infection rate of more than 60%, comparable with susceptible check TN1 (see table). These results contradict our previous view that virus resistance is more durable than vector resistance.

Eleven leafhopper-susceptible accessions were highly resistant to both strains. These accessions may be used as sources